

A systematic and synonymic list of the Riodinidae and the Lycaenidae (part 1) of Western Palearctic butterflies hyperlinked to the original descriptions (Lepidoptera, Papilionoidea)

Submitted: 13.v.2026 | Accepted: 10.vi.2026 | Published online: 30.vi.2026.

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.20156133](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20156133)

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Abstract

A systematic and synonymic list of the Riodinidae and the Lycaenidae (part I) butterflies of the Western Palearctic is presented, with all names hyperlinked to their original descriptions. The work covers taxonomic hierarchy from family to species level, incorporating historical synonyms, typification details, and bibliographic references, providing a comprehensive and navigable tool for lepidopterists and taxonomists.

Key words

Lepidoptera — Papilionoidea — Riodinidae — Nemeobinae — Lycaenidae — Aphnaeinae — Lycaeninae — Theclinae — Western Palearctic — taxonomy — nomenclature — synonymy — systematic catalogue — type species — original descriptions — type locality — butterfly classification — historical entomology.

Introduction

The present paper deals with the classification of the West Palearctic representatives of the families *Riodinidae* and *Lycaenidae*, with particular emphasis on the subfamily *Nemeobiinae* and on three subfamilies of *Lycaenidae*: *Aphnaeinae*, *Lycaeninae* and *Theclinae*. Within the West Palearctic fauna, *Nemeobiinae* is represented by a single species only, whereas *Lycaenidae* comprises a considerably larger number of taxa and several additional subfamilies. Owing to this diversity, the remaining West Palearctic subfamilies of *Lycaenidae* will be treated separately in subsequent papers.

The habitus generally allows an easy identification of most species included in these groups. However, the examination of genitalia remains necessary in certain cases, particularly within the genus *Callophrys*, or for distinguishing closely related taxa such as *Lycaena candens* and *L. hippothoe*.

Despite the considerable progress achieved in recent years, several taxonomic and systematic problems still remain unresolved. Further phylogenetic studies will be required to clarify the specific or subspecific status of several taxa and to provide a more satisfactory generic arrangement, especially within the tribes *Lycaenini* and *Eumaeini*. Since these groups include closely related species occurring in both the Palearctic and Nearctic regions, future studies should adopt a comprehensive approach including taxa from the entire Holarctic region in order to achieve a more stable and natural classification.

Several species groups continue to present substantial taxonomic difficulties, and the status of some taxa remains uncertain, whether they should be regarded as distinct species, subspecies, or evolutionary significant units (ESUs). This uncertainty applies, for example, to taxa such as *Lycaena heracleana*, *Cigaritis estherae* and *Satyrium vandalousica*.

Regular updates to a comprehensive systematic and synonymic reference list are therefore essential. A dynamic, continuously maintained list offers clear advantages over fixed, paper-based publications, which cannot be revised once issued and may become outdated relatively quickly as new taxonomic insights emerge.

Family

Riodinidae Grote, 1895

[ORIG] Riodinidae Grote, 1895. Mitt. Roemer Mus. Hildesheim (1): [\[2\]](#), [\[4\]](#).

TG: *Riodina* Westwood, 1851.

[JH] Erycinidae Swainson, 1827. Phil. Mag. (2)1(3): [185](#).

TG: *Erycina* Fabricius, 1807. Mag. Insektenk. 6: [286](#), nec *Erycina* Lamarck, 1805. Ann. Mus. Hist. Nat. 6: [413](#).

Subfamily

Nemeobiinae Bates, 1868

- [ORIG] Nemeobiinae Bates, 1868. J. Linn. Soc., Zool. 9: [412](#).
TG: *Nemeobius* Stephens, 1827 (= *Hamearis* Hübner, [1819]).
- [JS] Hamearinae Tutt, 1906. Nat. Hist. Brit. Lepid. 8: [299](#).
TG: *Hamearis* Hübner, [1819].

Tribe

Nemeobiini Bates, 1868

- [ORIG] Nemeobiinae Bates, 1868. J. Linn. Soc., Zool. 9: [412](#).
TG: *Nemeobius* Stephens, 1827 (= *Hamearis* Hübner, [1819]).
- [JS] Hamearinae Tutt, 1906. Nat. Hist. Brit. Lepid. 8: [299](#).
TG: *Hamearis* Hübner, [1819].

Genus

Hamearis Hübner, [1819]

- [ORIG] *Hamearis* Hübner, [1819]. Verz. bekannt. Schmett.: [19](#).
TS: *Papilio lucina* Linnaeus, 1758 by subsequent designation by Curtis, 1830. Brit. Entomol. 5: [no. 316](#).
- [JS] *Nemeobius* Stephens, 1827. Illustr. Brit. Entomol. (Haustellata) 1(4): [28-29](#).
TS: *Papilio lucina* Linnaeus, 1758 by monotypy.

Hamearis lucina (Linnaeus, 1758)

- [ORIG] *Papilio lucina* Linnaeus, 1758. Syst. Nat. (ed. 10)1: [480](#).
TL: S England.
- [IFS] *Nemeobius lucina* ab. *primipara* Costantini, 1916. Atti Soc. Nat. Mat. Modena (5)3: [15](#).
TL: Monte Gibbio (Modena prov., Italy).
- [JS] *Nemeobius lucina* f. *semibrunnea* Vorbrodtt, 1917. In: Vorbrodtt & Müller-Rutz, Mitt. Schweiz. Entomol. Ges. 12(9-10): [443](#).
TL: Geneva (W Switzerland).
- [JS] *Nemeobius lucina* f. *fulvior* Rocci, 1923. Mem. Soc. Entomol. Ital. 2: [6-7](#).
TL: Piedmont (NW Italy).
- [JS] *Nemeobius lucina* var. *browni* Oberthür, 1923. In: Lhomme, Cat. Lépid. Fr. Belg.: 72.
TL: Cadaujac (Gironde, France).
- [JS] *Nemeobius lucina* race *praestans* Verity, 1923. In: Verity & Querci, Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 35(suppl.): [13](#).
TL: Vingone Valley, Florence (Tuscany, Italy).
- [JS] *Nemeobius lucina* race *parvifulvior* Verity, 1923. In: Verity & Querci, Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 35(suppl.): [14](#).
TL: Belstead Wood, Ipswich (Suffolk, UK).
- [JS] *Nemeobius lucina* race *thurneri* Dannehl, 1925. Entomol. Z. 39(2): [6](#).
TL: Karawanks (Carinthia, Austria).
- [JS] *Nemeobius lucina* var. *sorini* Pionneau, 1926. Échange 42(424): 7.
TL: Gèdre (Hautes-Pyrénées dep., S France).

[SN] *Hamearis lucina* race *primipara* Verity, 1943. Farfalle diurne Italia 2: 390-381.
Comb. nov. and Stat. nov. for *Nemeobius lucina* ab. *primipara* Costantini, 1916.

Family

Lycaenidae [Leach], [1815]

[ORIG] Lycaenida [Leach], [1815]. In: Brewster, Edinburgh Ency. 9(1): [129](#).

TG: *Lycaena* Fabricius, 1807.

[JH] Lycaenides Herrich-Schäffer, [1843]. Syst. Bearb. Schmett. Eur. 1(1): [16](#).

TG: *Lycaena* Fabricius, 1807.

Subfamily

Aphnaeinae Distant, [1884]

[ORIG] Aphnaria Distant, [1884]. Rhopal. Malanaya: [196](#), [233](#).

TG: *Aphnaeus* Hübner, [1819].

Tribe

Aphnaeini Distant, [1884]

[ORIG] Aphnaria Distant, [1884]. Rhopal. Malanaya: [196](#), [233](#).

TG: *Aphnaeus* Hübner, [1819].

Genus

Cigaritis Donzel, 1847

[ORIG] *Cigaritis* Donzel, 1847. Ann. Soc. entomol. Fr. (2)5: [528](#).

TS: *Cigaritis zohra* Donzel, 1847 by subsequent designation by Scudder, 1875. Proc. Am. Acad. Arts Sci. 10(2): [142](#).

[JH] *Zerythis* Lucas, 1849. Explor. Sci. Algérie, Zool. 3: [pl. 1, fig. 8](#).

TS: *Zerythis siphax* Lucas, 1849 by monotypy ; *nec Zerythis* Blanchard, 1840. Hist. Nat. Ins. 3: 463.

[JS] *Spindasis* Wallengren, 1857. Kongl. Svenska Vetensk.-Akad. Handl. (NF)2(4): [45](#).

TS: *Spindasis masilikazi* Wallengren, 1857 by original designation.

[JS] *Apharitis* Riley, 1925. Novit. Zool. 32: [78-79](#).

TS: *Polyommatus epargyros* Eversmann, 1854 by original designation.

Cigaritis zohra Donzel, 1847

[ORIG] *Cigaritis zohra* Donzel, 1847. Ann. Soc. entomol. Fr. (2)5: [528-529](#), [pl. 8, fig. 5-6](#).

TL: Algeria.

[JS] *Cigaritis* var. *jugurtha* Oberthür, 1876. Étud. Entomol. 1: [21](#).

TL: Saïda (Algeria).

[JS] *Cigaritis massinissa* Lucas, 1849. Explor. Sci. Algérie, Zool. 3: [364-365](#).

TL: Djebel Amour (Algeria).

- [JS] *Cigaritis zohra* ssp. *littoralis* Riley, 1925. Novit. Zool. 32: [75](#).
TL: Oran (Algeria).
- [JS] *Cigaritis zohra* ssp. *guercifi* Gallet, 2003. Linneana Belgica 19(3): [129-130, fig.](#)
TL: Guercif, Taza (N Morocco).
- [JS] *Cigaritis zohra* ssp. *cryptozohra* Tarrier & André, 2016. Alexanor 27(6): [364-367, fig.](#)
TL: Tizi-n-Taghatine, SE Taliouine (Anti-Atlas, Morocco).

***Cigaritis monticola* Riley, 1925**

- [ORIG] *Cigaritis zohra* ssp. *monticola* Riley, 1925. Entomologist 58: 270.
TL: Taghzeft Pass, Aghbalu Larbi (Morocco).
- [JS] *Cigaritis monticola* ssp. *micromonticola* Tarrier, 2019. Alexanor 28(7-8): [657-658, fig.](#)
TL: Tizi-n-Tamda, NE Ali-Mhammed (High Atlas, Morocco).

***Cigaritis allardi* Oberthür, 1909**

- [ORIG] *Cigaritis allardi* Oberthür, 1909. Étud. Lépid. comp. 3: [401-403](#).
TL: Sebdou (Tlemcen prov., Algeria).
- [JS] *Cigaritis allardi* ssp. *occidentalis* Le Cerf, 1923. Bull. Soc. Entomol. Fr. 28(15): [197-198](#).
TL: Aïn El-Harcha (Morocco).
- [JS] *Cigaritis allardi* ssp. *meridionalis* Riley, 1925. Novit. Zool. 32: [72](#).
TL: Djebel Mekter (Algeria).
- [JS] *Cigaritis allardi* ssp. *neomeridionalis* Tarrier, 2025. Gen. Cigaritis Morocco: [38, fig.](#)
TL: Tizi-n-Ouguerd-Zegzaoune (High Atlas, Morocco).

ESU *C. estherae* Brévignon, 1985

- [ORIG] *Cigaritis allardi* ssp. *estherae* Brévignon, 1985. Alexanor 13(7): 307-308, fig.
TL: Agadir (Morocco).

***Cigaritis siphax* Lucas, 1849**

- [ORIG] *Cigaritis siphax* Lucas, 1849. Explor. Scient. Algérie, Hist. nat. Anim. articul. 3: [362-363](#), pl. 1, [fig. 8a-c](#).
TL: Constantine (Algeria).
- [JS] *Cigaritis siphax* ab.(var.) *erythrea* Staudinger, 1892. Dt. Entomol. Z. 5(2): [280](#).
TL: Tunis (Tunisia).
- [JS] *Cigaritis zohra* ssp. *orientalis* Riley, 1925. Novit. Zool. 32: [76](#).
TL: Ksar El Boukhari (Algeria).

***Cigaritis myrmecophila* Dumont, 1922**

- [ORIG] *Cigaritis myrmecophila* Dumont, 1922. Bull. Soc. entomol. Fr. 1922(15): [217-218](#).
TL: Tozeur, Nefta (Tunisia).

Cigaritis acamas (Klug, 1834)

- [ORIG] *Lycaena acamas* Klug, 1834. Symb. Phys., Ins. 4: [\[40\]](#), [pl. 40, fig. 7](#).
TL: Syria.
- [JS] *Cigaritis acamas* var. *obscurata* Staudinger, 1901. In: Staudinger & Rebel, Cat. Lepid. pal. Faunengeb.: [76](#).
TL: Hadjin, Taurus (Turkey).
- [JS] *Apharitis acamas* ssp. *egyptiaca* Riley, 1925. Novit. Zool. 32: [88](#).
TL: Mokkatam Hills (Egypt).
- [JS] *Apharitis acamas* ssp. *cypriaca* Riley, 1925. Novit. Zool. 32: [89](#).
TL: Episkopis (Cyprus).
- [JS] *Cigaritis acamas* ssp. *dueldueli* Pfeiffer, 1932. Mitt. Munch. Entomol. Ges. 22(1): [38](#).
TL: Amanus Mts, Düldül Dagi (Turkey).

Subfamily

Lycaeninae [Leach], [1815]

- [ORIG] Lycaenida [Leach], [1815]. In: Brewster, Edinburgh Ency. 9(1): [129](#).
TG: *Lycaena* Fabricius, 1807.
- [JH] Lycaenides Herrich-Schäffer, [1843]. Syst. Bearb. Schmett. Eur. 1(1): [16](#).
TG: *Lycaena* Fabricius, 1807.

Tribe

Lycaenini [Leach], [1815]

- [ORIG] Lycaenida [Leach], [1815]. In: Brewster, Edinburgh Ency. 9(1): [129](#).
TG: *Lycaena* Fabricius, 1807.
- [JS] Lycaenides Herrich-Schäffer, [1843]. Syst. Bearb. Schmett. Eur. 1(1): [16](#).
TG: *Lycaena* Fabricius, 1807.
- [RJ] Chrysophanidi Scudder, 1889. Butt. east U.S. & Canada 2: [793](#).
TG: *Chrysophanus* Hübner, 1818 ; rejected by Opinion 541 (ICZN, 1959).

Genus

Lycaena Fabricius, 1807

- [ORIG] *Lycaena* Fabricius, 1807. In: Illiger, Mag. Insektenk. 6: [285-286](#).
TS: *Papilio phlaeas* Linnaeus, 1761 by subsequent designation by Curtis, [1828]. Brit. Entomol. 5: [12](#).
- [NN] *Lycia* Sodoffsky, 1837. Bull. Soc. Nat. Mosc. 10: [81-82](#).
TS: *Papilio phlaeas* Linnaeus, 1761 through Article 67.8 Code ICZN (*Lycia* is a replacement name for *Lycaena* Fabricius, 1807).
- [JS] *Rumicia* Tutt, 1906. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 18(5): [131](#).
TS: *Papilio phlaeas* Linnaeus, 1761 by original designation.

Subgenus

Helleia Verity, 1943

[ORIG] *Lycaena (Helleia)* Verity, 1943. Farfalle diurne Italia 2: [20](#), [48](#).

TS: *Papilio helle* [Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775 by original designation.

Lycaena helle ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)

[ORIG] *Papilio helle* [Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775. Ankündigung syst. Werkes Schmett. Wienergegend: [181](#).

TL: Vienna area (Austria).

[JS] *Papilio amphidamas* Esper, [1781]. Schmett. Abb. Nat.1(2): [46-48](#), [pl. 58](#), [fig. 4](#).

TL: Braunschweig (Lower Saxony, Germany).

[JH] *Papilio xanthe* Lang, 1789. Verz. Schmett. Gegend. Ausburg (ed. 2): [52](#).

TL: Leipzig (Saxony, Germany) ; *nec* [Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775: [181](#).

[JS] *Polyommatus amphidamas* var. *lapponica* Backhaus, 1876. Entomol. Monatsbl. 1: [40](#).

TL: Lapland (N Scandinavia).

[JS] *Chrysophanus amphidamas marchica* Hannemann, 1928. Int. Entomol. Z. 22(22): 210.

TL: Strausberg (Brandenburg, Germany).

[JH] *Heodes amphidamas* ssp. *pyrenaica* Deslandes, 1930. Bull. Soc. entomol. Fr. 15: [243](#).

TL: Porté (Pyrénées-Orientales, S France) ; *nec Lycaena orbitulus* var. *pyrenaica* Boisduval, 1840. Gen. Ind. Meth. Eur. Lepid.: [11](#).

[NN] *Lycaena amphidamas deslandesi* Hemming, 1932. Proc. R. entomol. Soc. Lond.7: [29](#).

Replacement name for *Heodes amphidamas pyrenaica* Deslandes, 1930.

[JS] *Lycaena (Heodes) amphidamas leonia* Beuret, 1936. Lambillionea 36: 272-276.

TL: Tramelan (Berner Jura, Switzerland).

[JS] *Lycaena helle arvernica* Bernardi & de Lesse, 1952. Rev. fr. Lépid. 13(13-14): 203, 211, fig.

TL: Super-Besse, Vallée de Chaudefour (Puy-de-Dôme dep., France).

[JS] *Lycaena (Helleia) helle* ssp. *hellesimilis* Beuret, 1952. Mitt. Entomol. Ges. Basel 2(8): [101-102](#).

TL: Meggen (Lucerne, Switzerland).

[JS] *Lycaena helle magdalenae* Guérin, 1959. Alexanor1(3): 88.

TL: Monts de la Madeleine (Loire dep., France).

[JS] *Lycaena helle* ssp. *perrettei* Weiss, 1977. Linn. Belg.6(10): [254-256](#), [fig.](#)

TL: Gérardmer (Vosges, France).

[JS] *Lycaena helle* ssp. *eneli* Betti, 1977. Alexanor10(2): 92, fig.

TL: Lac de Remoray (Doubs, France).

[JS] *Lycaena helle* ssp. *arduinnae* Meyer, 1980. Linn. Belg.8(3): 131-133, fig.

TL: Hoffelt, Hachiville (Luxembourg).

[JS] *Lycaena helle* ssp. *shchurovi* Gorbunov, 2001. Butt. Russia: [110](#).

TL: Lago-Naki plateau, near the Belorechensky pass (NW Caucasus, Krasnodar Krai, S Russian Federation).

Subgenus

Thersamonia Verity, 1919

[ORIG] *Thersamonia* Verity, 1919. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 31(2): [28](#).

TS: *Papilio thersamon* Esper, 1784 by original designation.

Lycaena thetis Klug, 1834

[ORIG] *Lycaena thetis* Klug, 1834. Symb. Phys., Ins. 4: [\[41\]](#), [pl. 40, fig. 17-18](#).

TL: Syria.

[JS] *Thersamonia thetis* ssp. *hephestos* Dils & Poorten, 1982. Phegea 13(4): [109-112, fig. 1-2](#).

TL: Taygetos (S Greece).

Lycaena thersamon (Esper, [1784])

[ORIG] *Papilio thersamon* Esper, [1784]. Schmett. Abb. Nat. 1(2): [176-177, pl. 89 \(cont. 39\), fig. 6](#).

TL: Volgograd (Russian Federation).

[ORIG] *Papilio xanthe* Hübner, [1800]. Samml. eur. Schmett. 1: [pl. 69, fig. 347-348](#), [1806]: [53](#).

TL: Volgograd (Russian Federation).

Lycaena phoebus (Blachier, 1905)

[ORIG] *Chrysophanus phoebus* Blachier, 1905. Bull. Soc. entomol. Fr. 1905(13): [212](#).

TL: Morocco.

Subgenus

Thersamolycaena Verity, 1957

[NN] *Thersamonia* (*Thersamolycaena*) Verity, 1957. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 69(10): 225.

TS: *Papilio dispar* Haworth, 1802 by original designation ; replacement name for *Disparia* Verity, 1943.

[JH] *Thersamonia* (*Disparia*) Verity, 1943. Farfalle diurne Ital. 2: 21, 58.

TS: *Papilio dispar* Haworth, 1802 by original designation ; *nec* Nagano, 1916.

[JS] *Lycaena* (*Rapsidia*) Sibatani, 1974. Austral. J. Entomol. 13(2): [109](#).

TS: *Papilio dispar* Haworth, 1802 by original designation.

Lycaena dispar ([Haworth], 1802)

[ORIG] *Papilio dispar* [Haworth], 1802. Prodrromus Lepid. Brit.: [3](#).

TL: England.

[JH] *Papilio hippothoe* [Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775. Ank. syst. Werkes Schmett. Wienerg.: [181](#).

TL: Austria ; *nec* *Papilio hippothoe* Linnaeus, 1761. Fauna Suec. (ed. 2): [274](#).

[NN] *Papilio rutilus* Werneburg, 1864. Beitr. Schmetterlingsk. 1: [390-391](#).

Replacement name for *Papilio hippothoe* [Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775.

[JS] *Chrysophanus dispar* var. *festivus* Krulikovsky, 1910. Rev. russe entomol.9: [300](#).

TL: Vyatka (Russian Federation)

- [JS] *Chrysophanus dispar* f. *continentalis* Courvoisier, 1912. Int. entomol. Z. 6(10): [65](#).
TL: Manche (NW France).
- [JS] *Chrysophanus dispar* var. *burdigalensis* Lucas, 1913. Int. entomol. Z. 6(40): [282](#).
TL: Bordeaux area (SW France).
- [JS] *Chrysophanus dispar* var. *batavus* Oberthür, 1923. Ét. lépid. comp. 21(2): 71-75, [pl. 570, fig. 4914, 4915](#).
TL: Friesland (Netherlands).
- [JS] *Thersamonia (Disparia) dispar* race *centralitaliae* Verity, 1943. Farfalle diurne Ital. 2: 61-62, fig. 53-58.
TL: Fosso dell'Abate a Viareggio (Lucca prov., Italy).
- [JS] *Lycaena (Heodes) dispar* ssp. *carueli* Le Moulton, 1945. Misc. Entomol.42(4): 55.
TL: N France.
- [JS] *Lycaena (Heodes) dispar* ssp. *verityi* Le Moulton, 1945. Misc. Entomol.42(4): 57.
TL: Italy, France.
- [JS] *Heodes dispar* ssp. *ramaini* Le Moulton, [1946]. Novit. Entomol. 11-12(1-4): 141.
TL: Ural Mountains (Russian Federation).
- [JS] *Lycaena dispar* ssp. *hungarica* Szabó, 1956. Folia Entomol. Hung. 9(13): [300-302](#).
TL: Kamaraerdő (Hungary).
- [JS] *Lycaena dispar* ssp. *gronieri* Bernardi, 1963. Alexanor3(2): 53.
TL: Aisne (Hauts-de-France, N France).

Subgenus

Paleochrysophanus Verity, 1943

- [ORIG] *Paleochrysophanus* Verity, 1943. Farfalle diurne Ital. 2: 23, 64.
TS: *Papilio hippothoe* Linnaeus, 1761 by original designation.
- [ND] *Paleochrysophanus* Verity, 1934. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 46(5, suppl.): [13, note](#).
TS: *Papilio hippothoe* Linnaeus, 1761 by original designation ; invalid because there is no generic diagnosis.

Lycaena hippothoe (Linnaeus, 1761)

- [ORIG] *Papilio hippothoe* Linnaeus, 1761. Fauna Suecica(Ed. 2): [274](#).
TL: S Sweden.
- [JS] *Papilio chryseis* [Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775. Ank. syst. Werkes Schmett. Wienerg.: [181](#).
TL: Austria.
- [JH] *Papilio euridice* Rottenburg, 1775. Naturforscher6: [28-29](#).
TL: Austria ; *nec* Johannson, 1763. Centuria Ins. Rar.: [23](#).
- [JS] *Papilio xenophon* Loche, 1801. Mém. Acad. Sci. Turin 6(2): [149-150, pl.8, n.10](#).
TL: Piedmont (NW Italy).
- [JH] *Papilio euridice* Esper, [1804].Schmett. Abb. Nat. Suppl. 1(1): [120, pl. 116, fig. 6-7](#).
nec Johannson, 1763. Centuria Ins. Rar.: [23](#).
- [JS] *Papilio eurydame* Hoffmannsegg, 1806. Mag. f. Insektenk.5: [178](#).
TL: Geneva (Switzerland).

- [JS] *Papilio eurybia* Ochsenheimer, 1808. Schmett. Europa1(2): [81-82](#).
TL: S Switzerland ; Piedmont (NW Italy).
- [JS] [*Polyommatus chryseis*] var. *stiberi* Gerhard, [1852]. Versuch Mon. europ. Schmett.(9): [19](#), [pl. 35, f. 1a-b](#).
TL: Lapland (N Scandinavia).
- [JS] *Polyommatus hippothoe* var. *italica* Calberla, 1887. Corr.-Bl. Entomol. Ver. Iris1(1)(4): [126](#).
TL: Gran Sasso (Abruzzo, C Italy).
- [JS] *Polyommatus hippothoe* var. *groningana* Ter Haar, 1900. Tijdschr. Entomol. 43(3-4): [242](#).
TL: Groningen (Netherlands).
- [JS] *Chrysophanus hippothoe* ssp. *cisalpina* Fruhstorfer, 1909. Int. entomol. Z.3(21): [120](#).
TL: Val Maggia, Fusio (Ticino, Switzerland).
- [JS] *Chrysophanus hippothoe* f. *valderiana* Turati & Verity, 1911. Bull. Soc. entomol. Ital.42: [243-244](#).
TL: Valdieri (Piedmont, NW Italy).
- [JS] *Chrysophanus hippothoe mirus* Verity, 1913. J. Linn. Soc. (Zool.) 32(215): [188](#), [191](#).
TL: Pyrenees (France, Spain).
- [JS] *Chrysophanus hippothoe* var. *stieberioides* Ebert, 1926. Dt. entomol. Z. Iris 40: [35](#).
TL: Oberstdorf (S Bavaria, Germany).
- [JS] *Palaeochrysophanus hippothoe* race *paraerydice* Verity, 1943. Farfalle diurn. Ital. 2: 69.
TL: Val Susa, Bardonecchia (Italy).
- [JS] *Chrysophanus hippothoe* ssp. *parrai* Agenjo, 1944. Eos 20(1-2): [78-79, pl. 2, f. 4-6](#).
TL: Laguna de Camero (La Rioja, N Spain).
- [JS] *Palaeochrysophanus hippothoe* ssp. *engadiniana* Beuret, 1953. Mitt. entomol. Ges. Basel (n.f.)3(1): [6-7](#).
TL: Grisons, Engadine (Switzerland).
- [JS] *Palaeochrysophanus hippothoe* ssp. *bernardii* Beuret, 1955. Mitt. entomol. Ges. Basel (n.f.)5(7): [113-114](#).
TL: Cévennes (France).
- [JS] *Lycaena hippothoe* ssp. *sumadiensis* Szabó, 1956. Folia Entomol. Hung. 9(13): [304](#).
TL: Kaposvár (Hungary).
- [JS] *Lycaena (Palaeochrysophanus) hippothoe* ssp. *curti* Fernández Vidal, 1992. Guia Marip. diurn. Galicia: 94.
TL: Galicia (NW Spain).

***Lycaena candens* (Herrich-Schäffer, [1844])**

- [ORIG] *Polyommatus candens* Herrich-Schäffer, [1844]. Syst. Bearb. Schmett. Eur. 1(7) : [pl. 49, fig. 229-231](#) ; [1845] 1(10): [133](#).
TL: Turkey.
- [JS] *Chrysophanus hippothoe* ssp. *leonhardi* Fruhstorfer, 1917. Entomol. Rundsch.34(4): [16](#).
TL: Bulgaria.
- [JH] *Palaeochrysophanus candens* ssp. *pfeifferi* Beuret, 1952. Mitt. entomol. Ges. Basel(n.f.) 2(7): [59-60](#).
TL: Achalzich (Samtskhe-Javakheti, Georgia).

Subgenus

Heodes Dalman, 1816

- [ORIG] *Zephyrus (Heodes)* Dalman, 1816. K. svenska Vetensk.-Akad. Handl.(1b) 1816: [63](#).
TS: *Papilio virgaureae* Linnaeus, 1758 by subsequent designation by Crotch, 1872. Cist. Entomol. 1(4): [71](#).
- [JS] *Chysoptera* Zincken, 1817. Allg.-Lit. Ztg Halle 3(218): [75](#).
TS: *Papilio virgaureae* Linnaeus, 1758 by subsequent designation by Tutt, 1906. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 18(5): [131](#).
- [ISS] *Chrysoptera* Tutt, 1906. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 18(5): [131](#).
Incorrect subsequent spelling for *Chysoptera* Zincken, 1817.
- [JS] *Loweia* Tutt, 1906. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 18(5): [131](#).
TS: *Papilio dorilis* Hüfnagel, 1766 by original designation.
- [JS] *Palaeoloweia* Verity, 1934. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 46(5, suppl.): [13](#), [note](#).
TS: *Papilio tityrus* Poda, 1761 by original designation.
- [JS] *Heodes (Alciphronia)* Koçak, 1992. Misc. Pap., CESA (16): [2](#).
TS: *Papilio alciphron* Rottemburg, 1775 by original designation.

Lycaena ottomanus (Lefebvre, [1830])

- [ORIG] *Polyommatus ottomanus* Lefebvre, 1831. Mag. Zool. 1(2): [19\[1+2\]](#), [pl. 46](#), [fig. 3a-b](#).
TL: Balıkesir (W Turkey).
- [JH] *Lycaena legeri* Freyer, 1830. Beitr. eur. Schmett.3(23): [125-126](#), [pl. 133](#), [fig. 1](#).
TL: Istanbul (Turkey).

Lycaena bleusei (Oberthür, 1884)

- [ORIG] *Polyommatus xanthe* f.(var.) *bleusei* Oberthür, 1884. Étud. Entomol. 8: [15 \(nota\)](#), [\[52\]](#).
TL: El Pardo (Madrid, C Spain).

Lycaena virgaureae (Linnaeus, 1758)

- [ORIG] *Papilio virgaureae* Linnaeus, 1758. Syst. Nat. (ed. 10)1: [484](#).
TL: Sweden.
- [JS] *Polyommatus virgaureae* var. *montana* Meyer-Dür, 1852. Verz. Schmett. Schweiz 1: [53](#).
TL: Glacier du Rhône (Valais, Switzerland).
- [JS] *Lycaena oranula* Freyer, 1845. Neuere Beitr. Schmett. 5(76): [120-121](#), pl. 455, fig. 1-2.
TL: Lapland (N Scandinavia).
- [JS] *Polyommatus miegii* Vogel, 1857. Allg. Dt. naturhist. Ztg. 3: [201-206](#), [pl. 6](#), [fig. 1-4](#).
TL: Sierra de Guadarrama, Escorial (C Spain).
- [JS] *Polyommatus virgaureae zermattensis* Fallou, 1865. Ann. Soc. Entomol. Fr. (4)5: [101-102](#), [pl. 2](#), [fig. 3](#).
TL: Zermatt (Valais, Switzerland).
- [JS] *Polyommatus virgaureae* var. *apennina* Calberla, 1888. Corr.-Bl. Entomol. Ver. Iris 1(1)(4): [125](#).
TL: Gran Sasso, Boscolungo (C Italy).
- [JS] *Polyommatus virgaureae* var. *aureomicans* Heyne, 1897. Soc. Entomol.12(2): [9](#).
TL: Taurus, Mersin (S Turkey).

- [JS] *Chrysophanus virgaureae* var. *armeniaca* Bang-Haas, 1906. Dt. entomol. Z. Iris 19(3): [128-129](#).
TL: Tschorum (Armenia).
- [JH] *Chrysophanus virgaureae* var. *caucasica* Jachontov, 1908. Rev. Russe Entomol. 8: [291](#).
TL: N Caucasus (Russian Federation) ; nec *Lycaena corydon* var. *caucasica* Lederer, 1870.
- [JS] *Crysophanus* [sic] *virgaureae* ssp. *athanagild* Fruhstorfer, 1908. Int. entomol. Z. 2(29): [194](#).
TL: Grisons, Engadine (Switzerland).
- [JS] *Chryhsophanus* [sic] *virgaureae* ssp. *juvara* Fruhstorfer, 1908. Int. entomol. Z. 2(29): [195](#).
TL: Passau (Bavaria, S Germany).
- [JS] *Chrysophanus virgaureae* ssp. *osthelderi* Fruhstorfer, 1909. Int. entomol. Z. 3(20): [113](#).
TL: Fusio (Ticino, Switzerland) ; Formazza, Tosafall (Piedmont, NW Italy).
- [JS] *Chrysophanus virgaureae* ssp. *alexandrae* Fruhstorfer, 1909. Int. entomol. Z. 3(21): [120](#).
TL: Turgojak (Ural, Russian Federation).
- [JS] *Chrysophanus virgaureae* ssp. *pelusioti* Fruhstorfer, 1910. Entomol. Z. 24(26): [144](#).
TL: Cogne (N Italy).
- [JS] *Chrysophanus virgaureae* race *inalpinus* Verity, 1913. J. linn. Soc. (Zool.) 32(215): [187](#).
TL: Valdieri (Piedmont, NW Italy).
- [JS] *Chrysophanus virgaureae* ssp. *chrysorhoas* Fruhstorfer, 1917. Dt. entomol. Z. Iris 31(1-2): [33](#).
TL: Homburg (Germany).
- [JS] *Chrysophanus virgaureae* ssp. *cissites* Fruhstorfer, 1917. Dt. entomol. Z. Iris 31(1-2): [34](#).
TL: Gadmental (Bern, Switzerland).
- [JS] *Chrysophanus virgaureae* ssp. *theages* Fruhstorfer, 1917. Dt. entomol. Z. Iris 31(1-2): [40](#).
TL: Le Prese et Brusio, Poschlovtal (Grisons, Switzerland).
- [JS] *Lycaena virgaureae* ssp. *vera* Hemming & Graves, 1928. The Entomologist 61: 87.
TL: Haute-Loire dep. (France).
- [JS] *Lycaena virgaureae* ssp. *pyrenaeicola* Hemming & Graves, 1928. The Entomologist 61: 104.
TL: Pyrénées orientales dep. (France).
- [JS] *Lycaena virgaureae* ssp. *balcanicola* Hemming & Graves, 1928. The Entomologist 61: 106.
TL: Kostenetz (S Bulgaria).
- [JS] *Heodes virgaureae* race *gravesica* Verity, 1929. Bull. Soc. entomol. Fr. 1929(7): [129](#).
TL: Aigoual (Lozère dep., France).
- [JS] *Heodes virgaureae* race *mediomontana* Verity, 1929. Bull. Soc. entomol. Fr. 1929(7): [131](#).
TL: Col de Sestrières (Piedmont, NW Italy) ; Montgenèvre (Hautes-Alpes dep., SE France).
- [JS] *Heodes virgaureae* race *pyrenemontana* Verity, 1929. Bull. Soc. entomol. Fr. 1929(7): [131](#).
TL: Gèdre (Hautes-Pyrénées dep., France).
- [JS] *Chrysophanus virgaureae* ssp. *delicata* Higgins, 1930. The Entomologist 63(804): 99.
TL: Piedmont (NW Italy).
- [JS] *Chrysophanus virgaureae* ssp. *rhenana* Heydemann, 1943. Dt. entomol. Z. Iris 55: 99.
TL: Germany.
- [JS] *Lycaena virgaureae* ssp. *pyronitens* Szabó, 1956. Folia entomol. Hung. 9(13): [299](#), [340](#).
TL: Hungary.

- [JS] *Lycaena (Heodes) virgaureae denizae* Eckweiler & Rose, 1993. Nachr. Entomol. Ver. Apollo NF 13(3a): [356, pl. 1, f. 1-8](#).
TL: Isparta, Eğirdir, Aksu, Dedegöl Dağ (Turkey).
- [NN] *Lycaena virgaureae* nom. nov. *mikaeli* Tsvetkov, 2010. Caucasian Entomol. Bull.6(1): [99](#).
Replacement name for *Chrysophanus virgaureae caucasica* Jachontov, 1908.

Lycaena tityrus (Poda, 1761)

- [ORIG] *Papilio tityrus* Poda, 1761. Ins. Mus. Graec.: [77](#).
TL: Graz area (Austria).
- [JS] *Papilio acrion* Brünnich, 1763. In: Pontoppidan, Danske Atlas 1: [685-686, pl. 30, fig. \[1\]](#).
TL: Denmark.
- [JS] *Papilio dorilis* Hufnagel, 1766. Berlin. Mag. 2(1): [68-69](#).
TL: Berlin (Germany).
- [JS] *Papilio phocas* Rottemburg, 1775. Der Naturforscher 6: [29](#).
TL: Germany.
- [JS] *Papilio xanthe* [Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775. Ank. syst. Werkes Schmett. Wienerg.: [181](#).
TL: Vienna area (Austria).
- [JH] *Papilio circe* [Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775. Ank. syst. Werkes Schmett. Wienerg.: [181](#).
TL: Vienna area (Austria) ; *nec Papilio circe* Fabricius, 1775. Syst. entomol.: [495](#).
- [JH] *Papilio rubi* Geoffroy, 1785. Entomol. Paris 2: [245](#).
TL: Paris (France) ; *nec Papilio rubi* Linnaeus, 1758. Syst. Nat. (ed. 10)1: [483](#).
- [JS] *Papilio garbus* Fabricius, 1787. Mantissa Insect. 2: [81](#).
TL: Austria.
- [JS] *Polyommatus myopa* Latreille, 1805. Hist. nat. Crust. Ins. 14: [121](#).
TL: France, Germany.
- [JS] *Polyommatus circe* var. *subalpina* Speyer, 1851. Entomol. Ztg.12(11): [339](#).
TL: Patscher Kofel (Tirol, Austria).
- [JS] *Polyommatus xanthe* var. *montana* Meyer-Dür, 1852. Verz. Schmett. Schweiz1: [60](#).
TL: Gotthard Pass (Ticino, Switzerland).
- [JS] *Chrysophanus dorilis* var. *locarnensis* Tutt, 1903. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 15(9): [224](#).
TL: Locarno (Ticino, Switzerland).
- [JS] *Loweia dorilis* race *italorum* Verity, 1919. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 31(2): [29](#).
TL: Italy.
- [JS] *Chrysophanus dorilis* ssp. *reverdini* Stauder, 1921. Dt. entomol. Z. Iris 35: [30](#).
TL: Faito, Aspromonte (S Italy).
- [JS] *Palaeoloweia tityrus* race *pallidepicta* Verity, 1934. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 46(suppl.): [16](#).
TL: Mont Ventoux (Vaucluse dep., S France).
- [JS] *Palaeoloweia tityrus* race *praebileusei* Verity, 1934. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 46(suppl.): [17](#).
TL: Puerto de Pajares (Asturias, NW Spain).
- [JS] *Heodes (Chrysophanus) tityrus* race *catherinei* Verity, 1948. Var. géogr. saison. pap. diurn. Fr.: [58](#).
TL: Val de Héas (Hautes-Pyrénées dep., S France).

- [JS] *Heodes (Chrysophanus) tityrus* race *oceanitis* Verity, 1948. Var. géogr. saison. pap. diurn. Fr.: [58](#).
TL: Marsas, St. Côme (Gironde dep.), Puybelliard, Olonne (Vendée dep.) (W France).
- [JS] *Heodes (Chrysophanus) tityrus* race *mixtalpina* Verity, 1948. Var. géogr. saison. pap. diurn. Fr.: [60](#).
TL: Vallée du Boréon (Alpes-Maritimes dep., SE France).
- [JS] *Lycaena (Heodes) tityrus argentifex* Bálint, 1990. Janus Pannonius Múz. Évkönyve 34: [54-59, fig. 1-4](#).
TL: Békási-szoros, Kupás-p. (Romania).

***Lycaena alciphron* (Rottemburg, 1775)**

- [ORIG] *Papilio alciphron* Rottemburg, 1775. Naturforscher 6: [10-11](#).
TL: Berlin area (E Germany).
- [JH] *Papilio virgaeaureae* Hufnagel, 1766. Berlin. Mag. 2(1): [80-81](#).
TL: Berlin area (E Germany) ; *nec Papilio virgaeaureae* Linnaeus, 1758. Syst. Nat. (ed. 10)1: [484](#).
- [JS] *Papilio lampetie* [Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775. Ank. syst. Werkes Schmett. Wienerg.: [322](#).
TL: Vienna area (Austria).
- [JS] *Papilio gordius* Sulzer, 1776. Abg. Gesch. Ins. 1: [146](#).
TL: Bünden (Grisons, Switzerland).
- [JH] *Papilio hippothoe* Esper, [1777]. Schmett. Abb. Nat. 1(1): [342-343](#) [1779], [pl. 35, fig. 5](#) [1777].
TL: Germany ; *nec Papilio hippothoe* Linnaeus, 1761. Fauna Suec. (ed. 2): [274](#).
- [JS] *Papilio hiera* Fabricius, 1787. Mantissa Insect. 2: [80](#).
TL: Austria.
- [JH] *Papilio helle* Borkhausen, 1788. Naturg. eur. Schmett. 1: [146-147](#).
TL: Germany ; *nec Papilio helle* [Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775. Ank. syst. Werkes Schmett. Wienerg.: [181](#).
- [JS] *Papilio columbanus* Prunner, 1798. Lepid. Pedemont.: [76](#).
TL: Piedmont (NW Italy).
- [JS] *Polyommatus alciphron intermedia* Stefanelli, 1874. Bull. Soc. entomol. Ital. 6: [85](#).
TL: Tuscany (Italy).
- [JS] *Polyommatus alciphron* var. *melibaeus* Staudinger, 1878. Horae Soc. Entomol. Ross. 14(2-3): [231-232](#).
TL: Amasya (N Turkey).
- [JS] *Polyommatus cupreus* Cosmovici, 1892. Naturaliste 14(136): [255](#).
TL: Neamț (Romania).
- [JS] *Chrysophanes gordius* var. *granadensis* Ribbe, 1905. Soc. entomol. 20(18): [138](#).
TL: Andalusia (S Spain).
- [JS] *Chrysophanus alciphron* ssp. *isokrates* Fruhstorfer, 1909. Int. Entomol. Z. 3(21): [120](#).
TL: Simplon, Iselle (Switzerland) ; Val de Cogne (Aoste, NW Italy).
- [JS] *Chrysophanus alciphron* ssp. *romanorum* Fruhstorfer, 1909. Int. Entomol. Z. 3(21): [120](#).
TL: Rome (C Italy).
- [JS] *Chrysophanus alciphron* ssp. *gaudeolus* Fruhstorfer, 1909. Int. Entomol. Z. 3(21): [120](#).
TL: Zermatt (Valais, Switzerland) ; Lana (South Tyrol, SE Italy).
- [JS] *Polyommatus gordius diniensis* Oberthür, 1910. Ét. Lépid. comp. 4: [114](#), [667](#), [pl. 38, fig. 245](#).
TL: Digne (Alpes-de-Haute-Provence dep., SE France).

- [JS] *Polyommatus gordius rondoui* Oberthür, 1910. Ét. Lépid. comp. 4: [114](#), [667](#), [pl. 38, fig. 246](#).
TL: Gèdre (Hautes-Pyrénées dep., S France).
- [JS] *Polyommatus gordius nevadensis* Oberthür, 1910. Ét. Lépid. comp. 4: [114](#), [667](#), [pl. 38, fig. 248](#).
TL: Sierra Nevada (Andalusia, S Spain).
- [JS] *Polyommatus gordius bellieri* Oberthür, 1910. Ét. Lépid. comp. 4: [114](#), [667](#), [pl. 38, fig. 249-250](#).
TL: Madonie (Sicily, S Italy).
- [JS] *Chrysophanus alciphron* ssp. *aetnea* Turati, 1911. Soc. Entomol. 25(21): [81-82](#).
TL: Catane, Nicolosi Etnea (Sicily, S Italy).
- [JS] *Chrysophanus alciphron* ssp. *ruehli* Turati, 1911. Soc. Entomol. 25(21): [83](#).
TL: Cerchio (Abruzzo, C Italy).
- [IFS] *Chrysophanus alciphron gordius* s.-race *calabrus* Verity, 1913. Bull. Soc. entomol. ital. 45: [228](#), [pl. 1, fig. 43](#).
TL: Piani di Carmelia, Aspromonte (Calabria, S Italy).
- [JS] *Chrysophanus alciphron* ssp. *chairemon* Fruhstorfer, 1917. Entomol. Rdsch. 34(4): [16-17](#).
TL: Orsowa (Bulgaria) ; Herzegovina (Bosnia and Herzegovina).
- [JS] *Chrysophanus alciphron* ssp. *fruginus* Fruhstorfer, 1917. Entomol. Rdsch. 34(4): [17](#).
TL: Armenia.
- [JS] *Chrysophanus alciphron* ssp. *madytus* Fruhstorfer, 1917. Entomol. Rdsch. 34(4): [17](#).
TL: Petralia (Sicily, S Italy).
- [ND] *Chrysophanus alciphron* ssp. *gallon* Fruhstorfer, 1917. Entomol. Rdsch. 34(4): [17](#).
TL: Digne (Alpes-de-Haute-Provence dep., SE France) ; nomen nudum, not described.
- [JS] *Chrysophanus alciphron* ssp. *veronius* Fruhstorfer, 1917. Entomol. Rdsch. 34(4): [17](#).
TL: Gèdre (Hautes-Pyrénées dep., S France).
- [JS] *Chrysophanus alciphron* ssp. *epidelion* Fruhstorfer, 1917. Entomol. Rdsch. 34(4): [17-18](#).
TL: Alpes-Maritimes (SE France).
- [JS] *Chrysophanus alciphron* ssp. *deinaretton* Fruhstorfer, 1917. Entomol. Rdsch. 34(4): [18](#).
TL: Gran Sasso, Sibillini Mountains (C Italy).
- [JS] *Loweia alciphron* race *mirabilis* Verity, 1919. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 31(2): [28-29](#).
TL: Monte Senario, Vaglia (Tuscany, Italy).
- [JS] *Loweia alciphron* race *insignis* de Sagarra, 1924. Butll. Inst. Catal. Hist. nat. (2)4(9): [201](#).
TL: Albarracin (Aragón, Spain).
- [JS] *Loweia alciphron* race *paupercula* de Sagarra, 1924. Butll. Inst. Catal. Hist. nat. (2)4(9): [201-202](#).
TL: Puerto de Orihuela del Tremedal (Aragón, Spain).
- [JH] *Chrysophanus alciphron violacea* Pionneau, 1926. Échange 42(424): 7.
TL: Gironde (E France) ; *nec Polyommatus chryseis violacea* Oberthür, 1910. Ét. Lépid. comp. 4: [130](#).
- [JS] *Loweia alciphron* race *ultragordius* Verity, 1926. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 38(7/8): [105](#).
TL: Oulx (Piedmont, NW Italy).
- [NN] *Heodes (Chrysophanus) alciphron* race *oceani* Verity, 1943. Farfalle diurn. Ital. 2: 43.
Replacement name for *Chrysophanus alciphron violacea* Pionneau, 1922.
- [JS] *Heodes (Chrysophanus) alciphron* race *citragordius* Verity, 1943. Farfalle diurn. Ital. 2: 45-46.
TL: Turbigo (Lombardy, NW Italy).

- [JS] *Heodes (Chrysophanus) alciphron* race *minutepunctata* Verity, 1948. Var. géogr. saison. pap. diurn. Fr.: [62-63](#).
TL: Champ de tir de Nîmes (Gard dep., S France).
- [JS] *Heodes (Chrysophanus) alciphron* ssp. *rhaetica* Beuret, 1952. Mitt. entomol. Ges. Basel (NF) 2: [86](#).
TL: Ardez, Tarasp (Graubünden, Switzerland).
- [JS] *Lycaena alciphron* ssp. *cumanicus* Szabó, 1956. Folia entomol. Hung. (NS) 9(13): [305](#), [340](#).
TL: Peszér (Hungary).
- [JS] *Heodes alciphron* ssp. *ochsenfeldinus* Betti, 1977. Alexanor 10(2): 91.
TL: Germany.
- [JS] *Lycaena alciphron* ssp. *burgundiae* Bellenger & Descimon, 1977. Alexanor 10(4): 165.
TL: Bourgogne (NE France).
- [JS] *Lycaena alciphron* ssp. *morvandica* Bellenger & Descimon, 1977. Alexanor 10(4): 166.
TL: Morvan (France).
- [JS] *Heodes alciphron* ssp. *boyarensis* Verdugo-Páez, 1984. SHILAP 12(45): [56](#).
TL: Grazalema (Cádiz prov., S Spain).

ESU *L. heracleana* (Blachier, 1908)

- [JS] *Chrysophanus alciphron* var. *heracleana* Blachier, 1908. Ann. Soc. entomol. Fr. 77(2): [217](#).
TL: Atlas Mountains (Morocco).

Subgenus

Lycaena Fabricius, 1807

- [ORIG] *Lycaena* Fabricius, 1807. In: Illiger, Mag. Insektenk. 6: [285-286](#).
TS: *Papilio phlaeas* Linnaeus, 1761 by subsequent designation by Curtis, [1828]. Brit. Entomol. 5: [12](#).
- [NN] *Lycia* Sodoffsky, 1837. Bull. Soc. Nat. Mosc. 10: [81-82](#).
TS: *Papilio phlaeas* Linnaeus, 1761 through Article 67.8 Code ICZN (*Lycia* is a replacement name for *Lycaena* Fabricius, 1807).
- [JS] *Rumicia* Tutt, 1906. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 18(5): [131](#).
TS: *Papilio phlaeas* Linnaeus, 1761 by original designation.

Lycaena phlaeas (Linnaeus, 1761)

- [ORIG] *Papilio phlaeas* Linnaeus, 1761. Fauna Suec. (ed. 2): [285](#).
TL: Västmanland (Sweden).
- [JH] *Papilio virgaureae* Scopoli, 1763. Entomol. Carniol.: [180-181](#).
TL: Slovenia ; *nec* Linnaeus, 1758. Syst. Nat. (ed. 10)1: [484](#).
- [JS] *Papilio timeus* Cramer, [1777]. Uitl. Kap. 2(16): [137](#), [pl. 186](#), [fig. E-F](#).
TL: Izmir (Turkey).
- [JS] *Hesperia eleus* Fabricius, 1798. Suppl. Entomol. Syst.: [430-431](#).
TL: Germany.
- [JS] *Polyommatus turcicus* Gerhard, [1850]. Vers. Monogr. eur. Schmett. (2): [5](#), [pl. 5](#), [fig. 5](#).
TL: Turkey.

- [JS] *Polyommatus xanthe* var. *schmidtii* Gerhard, [1850]. Vers. Monogr. eur. Schmett. (3): [7](#), [pl. 10, fig. 3](#).
TL: Europe.
- [JS] *Polyommatus phlaeas* var. *cuprinus* Peyerimhoff, 1862. Cat. Lepid. Alsace: [13](#).
TL: Hohneck (Vosges, NE France).
- [JS] *Polyommatus phlaeas* var. *transiens* Fuchs, 1899. Jahrb. Nassauisch. Ver. Naturk. 52: [120](#).
TL: Loreley (Rhineland-Palatinate, Germany).
- [JS] *Chrysophanus phlaeas* var. *phlaeoides* Staudinger, 1901. In: Staudinger & Rebel, Cat. Lepid. pal. Fauneng.: [74](#).
TL: Madeira (Portugal).
- [JS] *Chrysophanus phlaeas* f. *polaris* Courvoisier, 1911. Entomol. Z. 24(49): [262](#).
TL: Lapland (N Norway).
- [JS] *Rumicia phlaeas* race *nigrioreleus* Verity, 1920. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 32(1): [5](#).
TL: Tuscany (Italy).
- [JS] *Rumicia phlaeas* race *varieleus* Verity, 1920. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 32(1): [5-7](#).
TL: Valdieri (Cuneo prov., Piedmont, NW Italy).
- [JS] *Rumicia (Chrysophanus) phlaeas* f. *cyrenaica* Turati, 1922. Atti Soc. ital. Sci. nat. Milano 60: [219-220](#).
TL: Uadi Derna (Cyrenaica prov., Libya).
- [JS] *Heodes phlaeas* race *hyperborea* Ford, 1924. Trans. Entomol. Soc. Lond. 1923(5): [739](#), [pl. 54, fig. 6](#).
TL: Arctic Norway.
- [JS] *Heodes phlaeas lusitanica* Bryk, 1940. Arkiv Zool. 32A(22): 20, pl. 6, fig. 37-38.
TL: Portugal.
- [JS] *Lycaena phlaeas* ssp. *hibernica* Goodson, 1948. The Entomologist 81: 177.
TL: Ireland.

Subgenus

Phoenicurusia Verity, 1943

- [ORIG] *Lycaena (Phoenicurusia)* Verity, 1943. Farfalle diurne Italia 2: [21](#).
TS: *Polyommatus phoenicurus* Lederer, 1870 by original designation.
- [JS] *Athamanthia* Zhdanko, 1983. Entomol. Obozr. 62: 161.
TS: *Lycaena athamantis* Eversmann, 1854 by original designation.

Lycaena japhetica Nekrutenko & Effendi, 1983

- [ORIG] *Lycaena japhetica* Nekrutenko & Effendi, 1983. Vestnik. Zool. 1983(4): [12](#).
TL: Dizavarchay river (Absheron distr., Azerbaijan).
- [ORIG] *Lycaena japhetica irghiza* Nekrutenko, 1985. Vestnik. Zool. 1985(4): [31-32, fig.](#)
TL: Irghiz (Aktjubinsk reg., Kazakhstan).

Subfamily

Theclinae Swainson, 1831

- [ORIG] Theclanae Swainson, 1831. Zool. Illustr. (2)2: [\[text pl. 85\]](#).
TG: *Thecla* Fabricius, 1807.

Tribe

Theclini Swainson, 1831

[ORIG] Theclanae Swainson, 1831. Zool. Illustr. (2)2: [\[text pl. 85\]](#).

TG: *Thecla* Fabricius, 1807.

Genus

Thecla Fabricius, 1807

[ORIG] *Thecla* Fabricius, 1807. In: Illiger, Mag. Insektenk. 6: [286](#).

TS: *Papilio betulae* Linnaeus, 1758 by subsequent designation by Swainson, 1821. Zool. Illustr. 2: 482.

[JS] *Theclaria* Rafinesque, 1815. Analyse Nat.: [128](#).

TS: *Papilio betulae* Linnaeus, 1758 by monotypy.

[JS] *Zephyrus* Dalman, 1816. K. svenska Vetensk.-Akad. Handl. (1b) 1816: [62](#).

TS: *Papilio betulae* Linnaeus, 1758 by original designation.

[JS] *Aurotis* Dalman, 1816. K. svenska Vetensk.-Akad. Handl. (1b) 1816: [63](#).

TS: *Papilio betulae* Linnaeus, 1758 by monotypy.

[JS] *Ruralis* Tutt, 1906. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 18(5): [130](#).

TS: *Papilio betulae* Linnaeus, 1758 by original designation.

[JS] *Iozephyrus* Wang & Fan, 2002. Butt. Fauna Sinica, Lycaenidae: 30.

TS: *Thecla betulina* Staudinger, 1887 by original designation.

Thecla betulae Fabricius, 1807

[ORIG] *Papilio betulae* Linnaeus, 1758. Syst. Nat. (ed. 10)1: [482](#).

TL: Sweden.

[JS] *Papilio apelles* Villers, 1789. Caroli Linnei Entomol. 2: [536](#).

TL: Lyon (C France).

[JS] *Thecla betulae* var. *spinosa* Gerhard, [1850]. Vers. Monogr. eur. Schmett. (2): [3](#), [pl. 3](#), [fig. 2](#).

TL: Europa.

Genus

Favonius Sibatani & Ito, 1942

[ORIG] *Favonius* Sibatani & Ito, 1942. Tenthredo 3(4): 327.

TS: *Dipsas orientalis* Murray, 1875 by original designation.

[JS] *Quercusia* Verity, 1943. Farfalle diurne Italia 2: 343.

TS: *Papilio quercus* Linnaeus, 1758 by original designation.

Favonius quercus (Linnaeus, 1758)

[ORIG] *Papilio quercus* Linnaeus, 1758. Syst. Nat. (ed. 10)1: [482](#).

TL: England (UK).

[JS] *Papilio epeus* Sulzer, 1776. Gesch. Ins. nach linn. Syst. 1: [145-146](#) ; 2: [pl. 18, fig. 10](#).

TL: Switzerland.

- [JS] *Thecla quercus* var. *bellus* Gerhard, [1850]. Vers. Monogr. eur. Schmett. (2): [4](#), [pl. 4, fig. 2](#).
TL: Europe.
- [JS] *Zephyrus quercus* var. *iberica* Staudinger, 1901. Cat. Lep. Pal. Fauneng. 1: [71](#).
TL: C and S Iberian Peninsula ; Mauretania (Morocco).
- [JS] *Thecla quercus* var. *violacea* Niepelt, 1914. Int. Entomol. Z. 8(26): [144](#).
TL: Magdeburg (Germany).
- [JS] *Bithis quercus* race *interjecta* Verity, 1919. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 31(3): [48](#).
TL: Italy.

Genus

Laeosopis Rambur, 1858

- [ORIG] *Laeosopis* Rambur, 1858. Cat. syst. lépid. Andal.: [33](#).
TS: *Papilio roboris* Esper, 1789 by monotypy.
- [JH] *Aurotis* Kirby, 1862. Man. Eur. Butt. : [87](#).
TS: *Papilio roboris* Esper, 1789 by monotypy ; *nec Aurotis* Dalman, 1816. K. svenska Vetensk.-Akad. Handl. (1b) 1816: [63](#).

Laeosopis roboris (Esper, [1793])

- [ORIG] *Papilio roboris* Esper, [1793]. Schmett. Abb. Nat.Suppl. 1(1): [59-60](#), [pl. 103 \(cont. 58\), fig. 5](#).
TL: Frankfurt (Hesse, Germany).
[very likely error, probably SW Europe]
- [JS] *Papilio evippus* Hübner, 1793. Samml. Ausserl. Vög. Schmett.: [11](#), pl. [56-57](#).
TL: -.
- [JS] *Papilio evippus* Hübner, [1800]. Samml. eur. Schmett. 1: [pl. 73, fig. 366-367](#), [1806]: [55-56](#).
TL: Spain.
- [JS] *Laeosopis roboris* var. *lusitanica* Staudinger, 1892. Dt. Entomol. Z. 4(2): [232](#).
TL: Algarve (S Portugal).
- [JS] *Jamides roboris* race *escorialensis* Oberthür, 1910. Ét. Lépid. Comp. 4: [57](#).
TL: El Escorial (C Spain).
- [JS] *Laeosopis roboris* race *demissa* Verity, 1943. Farfalle diurne Italia 2: 342.
TL: Guillaumes (Alpes Maritimes dep., SE France).
- [JS] *Laeosopis roboris magis* Agenjo, 1963. Bol. Serv. Plag. Forest. 6(12): 136.
TL: NW Spain.
- [JS] *Laeosopis roboris mudarra* Agenjo, 1963. Bol. Serv. Plag. Forest. 6(12): 137.
TL: NE Spain.
- [JS] *Laeosopis roboris higginsi* Agenjo, 1963. Bol. Serv. Plag. Forest. 6(12): 138.
TL: Granada (S Spain).
- [JS] *Laeosopis roboris portaensis* Betti, 1977. Alexanor 10(2): 93.
TL: Porté (Pyrénées-Orientales dep., S France).
- [JS] *Laeosopis roboris thiersi* Betti, 1977. Alexanor 10(2): 94.
TL: Lamalou-les-Bains (Hérault dep., S France).

Tribe

Deudorigini Doherty, 1886

[ORIG] Deudoriginae Doherty, 1886. J. asiat. Soc. Bengal. (2) 55(2): [110](#).

TG: *Deudorix* Hewitson, 1863.

Genus

Deudorix Hewitson, 1863

[ORIG] *Deudorix* Hewitson, 1863. Ill. diurn. Lepid. Lycaenidae 1: [16-17](#).

TS: *Dipsas epijarbas* Moore, 1858 by original designation.

[JS] *Virachola* Moore, [1881]. Lepid. Ceylon 1(3): [104](#).

TS: *Deudorix perse* Hewitson, 1863 by original designation.

Deudorix livia (Klug, 1834)

[ORIG] *Lycaena livia* Klug, 1834. Symb. Phys., Ins. 4: [[39-40](#)], [pl. 40, fig. 3-4](#).

TL: Egypt.

Tribe

Tomarini Eliot, 1973

[ORIG] Tomarini Eliot, 1973. Bull. Brit. Mus. (N.H.) Entomol. 28(6): [439](#).

TG: *Tomares* Rambur, [1840].

Genus

Tomares Rambur, [1840]

[ORIG] *Tomares* Rambur, [1840]. Faune entomol. Andal. 2(5): 261.

TS: *Papilio ballus* Fabricius, 1787 by monotypy.

Tomares ballus (Fabricius, 1787)

[ORIG] *Papilio ballus* Fabricius, 1787. Mantissa Ins. 2: [80](#).

TL: Spain.

[JS] *Tomares (Thestor) ballus* ssp. *mareoticus* Graves, 1918. Entomologist 51(660): [97-98](#), [pl. 1, fig. 1-2](#).

TL: Dekehla (Egypt).

[JS] *Thestor ballus cyrenaica* Turati, 1924. Atti Soc. Ital. Sci. Nat. 63: [35-36](#), pl. 1, fig. 14-16.

TL: Berca e Tocra, Benghazi (Libya).

[JS] *T. ballus* race *phychrokoilios* Forbes, 1929. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 41(1): [10](#).

TL: Ronda (S Spain).

[JS] *Thestor ballus* race *catalonica* Sagarra, 1930. Butll. Inst. catal. Hist. nat. (2)10(7): [116](#).

TL: Vallvidrera, Sant Medi (Catalonia, NE Spain).

Tomares mauritanicus (Lucas, 1849)

- [ORIG] *Polyommatus mauritanicus* Lucas, 1849. Explor. Scient. Algérie, Hist. nat. Anim. articul. 3: [360](#), pl. 1, [fig. 9a-c](#).
TL: Béjaïa (Algeria).
- [JS] *Tomares mauretanicus* [sic] ssp. *amelnorum* Tarrier, 1998. Alexanor 20(2): 120, fig. 23-24.
TL: Aït-Baha (Anti-Atlas, Morocco).
- [JS] *Tomares mauritanicus antonius* Brévignon, 1985. Alexanor 13(8): 342, fig.
TL: Col de Zad (Middle-Atlas, Morocco).

Tomares nogelii (Herrich-Schäffer, [1851])

- [ORIG] *Thecla nogelii* Herrich-Schäffer, [1851]. Syst. Bearb. Schmett. Eur. 1: [pl. 110, fig. 529-532](#) ; 6(Nachtrag): [33-34](#) [1852].
TL: Amasia (Turkey).
- [JS] *Thestor nogelii* var. *dobrogensis* Caradja, 1895. Dt. Entomol. Z. 8: [34](#).
TL: Tulcea (Dobruja, Romania).

Tomares callimachus (Eversmann, 1848)

- [ORIG] *Lycaena callimachus* Eversmann, 1848. Bull. Soc. imp. nat. Mosc. 21(3): [208-210](#).
TL: Helenendorf (= Goygol, [Azerbaijan](#)).
- [JS] *Tomares callimachus* ssp. *tauricus* Korb & Yakovlev, 1998. *Lambillionea* 98(1): 141.
TL: Sudak (Crimea).

Tribe

Eumaeini Doubleday, 1847

- [ORIG] Eumaeidae Doubleday, 1847. List Spec. lepid. Ins. Coll. Brit. Mus. (2): [20](#).
TG: *Eumaeus* Hübner, [1819].

Genus

Callophrys Billberg, 1820

- [ORIG] *Callophrys* Billberg, 1820. Enum. Ins. Mus. Billb.: [80](#).
TS: *Papilio rubi* Linnaeus, 1758 by subsequent designation by Scudder, 1875. Proc. Am. Acad. Arts Sci. 10(2): [132](#).
- [JH] *Lycus* Hübner, [1819]. Verz. bekannt. Schmett.: [74](#).
TS: *Papilio rubi* Linnaeus, 1758 by subsequent designation by Scudder, 1875. Proc. Am. Acad. Arts Sci. 10(2): [210](#) ; *nec* Fabricius, 1787. Mantissa Ins. 1: 163.

Callophrys avis Chapman, 1909

- [ORIG] *Callophrys avis* Chapman, 1909. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 21(6): [130-131](#).
TL: S France.
- [JS] *Callophris* [sic] *avis* f. *semipallida* Barragué, 1954. Bull. Soc. Hist. Nat. Afr. N. 45(3-4): 185.
TL: Algeria.
- [JS] *Callophrys avis* ssp. *barraguei* Dujardin, 1972. Entomops 4(25): 7-8, fig. 1.
TL: Kaddous (Algeria), Ifrane (Morocco).

- [JS] *Callophrys avis* ssp. *lhafii* Tarrier, 2017. Alexanor 28(2): [105-106, fig. 4-5](#).
TL: Ait-Iftene (SW Anti-Atlas, Morocco).
- [JS] *Callophrys rubi* [sic] ssp. *pumilio* Tarrier, 2017. Alexanor 28(2): [108-110, fig. 7](#).
TL: Tizi-Tazouguart (Middle Atlas, Morocco).

Callophrys suaveola (Staudinger, 1881)

- [ORIG] *Thecla rubi* var. *suaveola* Staudinger, 1881. Entomol. Ztg. 42(7-9): [279-280](#).
TL: Lepsy Valley (Kazakhstan).
- [JS] *Callophrys butlerovi* Migranov, 1992. Zool. Ž.71(5): 135-140, fig.
TL: S Ural (Russian Federation).

Callophrys rubi (Linnaeus, 1758)

- [ORIG] *Papilio rubi* Linnaeus, 1758. Syst. Nat. (ed. 10)1: [483](#).
TL: Sweden.
- [JS] *Papilio caecus* Geoffroy, 1785. Entomol. Paris. 2: [245-246](#).
TL: Paris (France).
- [JS] *Thecla rubi* var. *borealis* Krulikovskiy, 1890. Bull. Soc. imp. Nat. Moscou (n.s.)4(2): [217-218](#).
TL: Kazan (Tatarstan, Russia Federation).
- [JS] *Thecla rubi* var. *polaris* Krulikovskiy, 1893. Soc. Entomol. 7(21): [164](#).
TL: Vyatka Governorate (Volga-Vyatka, Russia Federation).
- [JS] *Callophrys rubi* var. *fervida* Staudinger, 1901. Cat. Lep. Pal. Fauneng. 1: [70](#).
TL: S Iberian Peninsula ; Mauretania ; ...
- [JS] *Callophrys rubi* var. *intermedia* Tutt, [1907]. Nat. Hist. Brit. Lepid. 9: 91.
TL: S Europe.
- [JS] *Callophrys rubi* race *virgatus* Verity, 1913. J. linn. Soc. (Zool.) 32(215): [187](#).
TL: C and S Europe (Germany ?).
- [JS] *Callophrys rubi* var. *foulquieri* Revertegat, 1914. Bull. Soc. Hist. Nat. Afr. N. 5(6): [154-155, fig. 2-4](#).
TL: Bône (= Annaba, NE Algeria).
- [JS] *Callophrys rubi* var. *leucosticta* Stauder, 1923. Z. Wiss. Ins.-Biol. 18(3-4): [66](#).
TL: NE Italy.

Callophrys chalybeitincta Sovinsky, 1905

- [ORIG] *Callophrys rubi* var. *chalybeitincta* Sovinsky, 1905. Rev. Russ. Entomol. 5(3-4): [109](#).
TL: Derbent (Daghestan, Russian Federation).
- [JS] *Callophrys rubi* var. *caerulescens* Bang-Haas, 1912. Dt. Entomol. Z. 26(2): [106](#).
TL: Elizavetpol (Azerbaijan).
- [JS] *Callophrys rubi* var. *schamyl* Sheldon, 1914. Entomologist 47(617): [272](#).
TL: Novorossiysk (South Caucasus, Russian Federation).
- [JS] *Callophrys chalybeitincta nigra* Stradomsky, 2005. Cauc. Entomol. Bull. 1(1): [85-86, fig. 1](#).
TL: Rostov-on-Don, Kumzhensky forest (North Caucasus, Russian Federation).

Genus

Neolycaena Nicéville, 1890

[ORIG] *Neolycaena* Nicéville, 1890. Butt. India Burmah Ceylon 3: [64-65](#).

TS: *Lycaena sinensis* Alphéraky, 1881 by original designation.

[JS] *Rhymnaria* Zhdanko, 1983. Entomol. Obozr. 62(1): 150.

TS: *Lycaena rhymnus* Evesmann, 1832 by original designation.

Neolycaena rhymnus (Eversmann, 1832)

[ORIG] *Lycaena rhymnus* Eversmann, 1832. Nouv. Mém. Soc. imp. nat. Moscou 2: [350](#), [pl. 19, fig. 1-2](#).

TL: S Ural (Kazakhstan ; Russian Federation).

Genus

Satyrium Scudder, 1876

[ORIG] *Satyrium* Scudder, 1876. Bull. Buff. Soc. nat. Sci. 3(15): [106](#).

TS: *Lycaena fuliginosa* Edwards, 1861 by original designation.

[JH] *Argus* Gerhard, [1850]. Versuch Monogr. eur. Schmett. (8): [4](#).

TS: *Lycaena ledereri* Boisduval, 1848 by monotypy ; *nec Argus* Bohadsch, 1761.

[JS] *Callipsyche* Scudder, 1876. Bull. Buffalo Soc. Nat. Sci. 3: [106-107](#).

TS: *Thecla behrii* Edwards, 1870 by original designation.

[JS] *Fixsenia* Tutt, [1907]. Nat. Hist. Brit. Lepid. 9: [142](#).

TS: *Thecla herzi* Fixsen, 1887 by original designation.

[JH] *Leechia* Tutt, [1907]. Nat. Hist. Brit. Lepid. 9: [142](#).

TS: *Thecla thalia* Leech, 1893 by original designation ; *nec Leechia* South, 1901 ; replaced by *Strymonidia* Tutt, [1908].

[JH] *Strymon* Hübner, [1819] sensus Tutt, [1907]. Nat. Hist. Brit. Lepid. 9: [142](#), [192-195](#).

TS: *Papilio pruni* Linnaeus, 1758 by original designation.

[JH] *Felderia* Tutt, [1907]. Nat. Hist. Brit. Lepid. 9: [142](#).

TS: *Thecla w-album eximia* Fixsen, 1887 by original designation ; *nec Felderia* Walsingham, 1887.

[JH] *Edwardsia* Tutt, [1907]. Nat. Hist. Brit. Lepid. 9: [142](#), [144-145](#).

TS: *Papilio w-album* Knoch, 1782 by original designation ; *nec Edwardsia* Costa, 1838 ; replaced by *Chattendenia* Tutt, [1908].

[JH] *Kuglia* Tutt, [1907]. Nat. Hist. Brit. Lepid. 9: [142](#).

TS: *Papilio spini* [Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775 by original designation ; *nec Klugia* Robineau-Desvoidy, 1863.

[JH] *Kollaria* Tutt, [1907]. Nat. Hist. Brit. Lepid. 9: [142](#).

TS: *Thecla sassanides* Kollar, 1850 by original designation ; *nec Kollaria* Pictet, 1841.

[JH] *Erschoffia* Tutt, [1907]. Nat. Hist. Brit. Lepid. 9: [142](#).

TS: *Thecla lunulata* Erschoff, 1874 by original designation ; *nec Erschoffia* Swinhoe, 1900.

[JH] *Bakeria* Tutt, [1907]. Nat. Hist. Brit. Lepid. 9: [142](#).

TS: *Lycaena ledereri* Boisduval, 1848 by original designation ; *nec Bakeria* Kieffer, 1905.

[JS] *Nordmannia* Tutt, [1907]. Nat. Hist. Brit. Lepid. 9: [142-143](#).

TS: *Lycaena myrtale* Klug, 1834 by original designation.

- [NN] *Strymonidia* Tutt, [1908]. Nat. Hist. Brit. Lepid. 9: [483](#).
Replacement name for *Leechia* Tutt, [1907].
- [NN] *Chattendenia* Tutt, [1908]. Nat. Hist. Brit. Lepid. 9: [483](#).
Replacement name for *Edwardsia* Tutt, [1907].
- [NN] *Tuttiolia* Strand, 1910. Entomol. Rdsch. 27(22): [162](#).
Replacement name for *Kuglia* Tutt, [1907].
- [NN] *Superflua* Strand, 1910. Entomol. Rdsch. 27(22): [162](#).
Replacement name for *Kollaria* Tutt, [1907].
- [NN] *Pseudothecla* Strand, 1910. Entomol. Rdsch. 27(22): [162](#).
Replacement name for *Erschoffia* Tutt, [1907].
- [NN] *Thecliolia* Strand, 1910. Entomol. Rdsch. 27(22): [162](#).
Replacement name for *Felderia* Tutt, [1907].
- [JS] *Strymonidia* (*Necovatia*) Verity, [1949]. Var. géogr. saison. pap. diurn. Fr.: 183.
TS: *Papilio acaciae* Fabricius, 1787 by original designation.
- [JS] *Armenia* Dubatolov & Korshunov, 1984. Nov. maloizv. Vidy Fauny Sib. (17): 53.
TS: *Lycaena ledereri* Boisduval, 1848 by original designation.

Satyrium pruni (Linnaeus, 1758)

- [ORIG] *Papilio pruni* Linnaeus, 1758. Syst. Nat. (ed. 10)1: [482](#).
TL: Germany.
- [JS] *Papilio ptorsas* Hufnagel, 1766. Berlin. Mag. 2(1): 68-69.
TL: Berlin (Germany).

Satyrium ilicis (Esper, [1779])

- [ORIG] *Papilio ilicis* Esper, [1779]. Schmett. Abb. Nat. 1(1): [353-354](#) ; [1778]: [pl. 39 \(suppl. 15\), fig. 1b](#) (*P. pruni* var.).
TL: Uffenheim (Bavaria, Germany).
- [JS] *Papilio cerasi* Fabricius, 1787. Mantissa Ins. 1: [69](#).
TL: Austria.
- [JH] *Polyommatus lynceus* Godart, 1823. Tabl. méth. Lépid. Fr.: [47](#).
TL: Europe ; *nec* Drury, 1773.
- [JS] *Papilio cerri* Hübner, [1824]. Samml. eur. Schmett. 1: [pl. 175, fig. 863-866](#).
TL: Austria.
- [JS] *Thecla caudatula* Zeller, 1847. Isis von Oken 1847(1): [6-7](#).
TL: Austria.
- [JS] *Thecla lynceus* var. *bischoffii* Gerhard, [1850]. Vers. Monogr. eur. Schmett. (2): [3, pl. 2, fig. 4](#).
TL: Turkey.
- [JS] *Thecla ilicis* var. *cilicica* Holtz, 1897. Illustr. Wochenschr. Entomol. 2: [46](#).
TL: Cilicia (SE Turkey).
- [JS] *Thecla ilicis* race *inalpina* Turati & Verity, 1911. Bull. Soc. Entomol. Ital. 42: [272-273, pl. 1, fig. 12-13](#).
TL: Martigny (Valais, Switzerland).

- [JS] *Thecla ilicis* race *inornata* Turati & Verity, 1911. Bull. Soc. Entomol. Ital. 42: [272-273](#).
TL: Tuscany (Italy).
- [JS] *Thecla ilicis* var. *burdigalensis* Pionneau, 1937. Échange 53(469): 11.
TL: Gironde (E France).
- [JS] *Strymon (Nordmannia) ilicis* s.-race *fiorii* Verity, 1943. Farfalle diurn. Ital. 2: 358, pl. 19 fig. 30-32.
TL: Mesola (Ferrara prov., NE Italy).

Satyrium esculi (Hübner, [1804])

- [ORIG] *Papilio esculi* Hübner, [1804]. Samml. eur. Schmett. 1: [pl. 109, fig. 559-560](#), [1806]: [57](#).
TL: Portugal.
- [JS] *Thecla ilicioides* Gerhard, [1850]. Vers. Monogr. eur. Schmett. (3): [3, pl. 4, fig. 5](#).
TL: Ronda (Andalusia, S Spain).
- [JS] *Thecla ilicioides* var. *maculatus* Gerhard, [1850]. Vers. Monogr. eur. Schmett. (3): [3, pl. 4, fig. 4](#).
TL: Andalusia (S Spain).
- [JS] *Thecla ilicis* var. *mauretanica* Staudinger, 1892. Dt. Entomol. Z. 5(2): [279](#).
TL: Tunis (Tunisia) ; Collo, Constantine (NE Algeria).
- [JS] *Thecla esculi* f. *powelli* Oberthür, 1910. Ét. Lépid. comp. 4: [79, 675, pl. 49, fig. 403-404](#).
TL: Khenchela (Algeria).
- [JS] *Strimon esculi* race *camboi* Sagarra, 1926. Butll. Inst. Catal. Hist. nat. (2)6(6): [135-136](#).
TL: Vilamajor (Barcelona prov., NE Spain).
- [JS] *Strimon esculi* race *neglecta* Sagarra, 1926. Butll. Inst. Catal. Hist. nat. (2)6(6): [136](#).
TL: Queralps (Girona prov., NE Spain).
- [JS] *Strymon ilicis pseudoesculi* Bryk, 1940. Arkiv Zool. 32A(22): 19.
TL: Spain.
- [ND] *Nordmannia esculi* ssp. *reisseri* Beuret. In: Bros & Schmidt-Koehl, 1979. Mitt. Entomol. Ges. Basel 29(1) : [12, 16](#).
TL: Xauen (Morocco) ; nomen nudum, published without description.

Satyrium w-album (Knoch, 1782)

- [ORIG] *Papilio w-album* Knoch, 1782. Beitr. Insektengesch. 2: [85-88, pl. 6, fig. 1-2](#).
TL: Leipzig (E Germany).
- [JS] *Papilio cerasi* Fabricius, 1787. Mantissa Ins. 2: [69](#).
TL: Austria.
- [JS] *Papilio w-latinum* Lang, 1789. Verz. Schmett. Gegend. Ausburg (ed. 2): [46](#).
TL: Leipzig (E Germany).
- [JS] *Thecla w-album* var. *meridionalis* Schultz, 1906. Nyt Mag. Naturvidensk. 44: [109-110](#).
TL: Nice, Cannes (SE France).
- [JS] *Thecla w-album* var. *majuscula* Jachontov, 1911. Izv. Kavk. Muz. 5: [313](#).
TL: Borzom (= Borjomi, C Georgia).

Satyrium spini ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)

- [ORIG] *Papilio spini* [Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775. Ankündigung syst. Werkes Schmett. Wienergegend: [186](#).
TL: Vienna area (Austria).
- [JH] *Papilio lynceus* Esper, [1778]. Schmett. Abb. Nat. 1(1): [pl. 39, fig. 3](#) ; [1779]: [356-357](#).
TL: Germany ; *nec* Drury, 1773. Illustr. Nat. Hist. 1: [12](#), [pl. 7, fig. 1](#), [index](#).
- [JS] *Lycaena melantho* Klug, 1834. Symb. Phys., Ins. 4: [\[40\]](#), [pl. 40, fig. 10-11](#).
TL: Syria.
- [JS] *Thecla spini* var. *major* Oberthür, 1910. Ét. Lépid. comp. 4: [69](#).
TL: Alpes Maritimes (SE France).
- [JS] *Thecla linceus brevicaudis* Vorbrodt & Müller-Rutz, 1911. Schmett. Schweiz 1: [106](#).
TL Zermatt (Valais, Switzerland).
- [JS] *Thecla (Klugia) spini* race *minuta* Verity, 1919. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 31(3): [48](#).
TL: Sibillini Mountains (C Italy).
- [JS] *Strymon lynceus* ssp. *anatolicus* Lattin, 1950. Rev. Fac. Sci. Istanbul, Sci. Nat. 15(4): [323, pl. 2, fig. 5](#).
TL: Akşehir (Konya prov., Turkey).

ESU S. vandalusica (Lederer, 1853)

- [ORIG] *Thecla spini* var. *vandalusica* Lederer, 1853. Verh. zool.-bot. Ver. Wien 2 (Abhandl.): [19, 34](#).
TL: Andalusia (S Spain).
- [JS] *Strymon spini* race *bofilli* Sagarra, 1924. Butll. Inst. Catal. Hist. nat. (2)4(9): [200](#).
TL: Albarracin (Aragón, Spain).
- [JS] *Strymon spini* race *leonensis* Manley, 1970. In: Manley & Allcard, Field Guide Butt. Burn. Spain: 114, pl. 35, fig. 29.
TL: Riaño (León prov., N Spain).

Satyrium acaciae (Fabricius, 1787)

- [ORIG] *Papilio acaciae* Fabricius, 1787. Mantissa Ins. 2: [69](#).
TL: S Russia (Russian Federation).
- [JS] *Thecla acaciae* f. *nostras* Courvoisier, 1913. Int. Entomol. Z. 7(38): [252](#).
TL: Europe.
- [JS] *Thecla (Nordmannia) acaciae* race *italica* Verity, 1919. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 31(3): [48](#).
TL: Tuscany (Italy).
- [JS] *Strymon acaciae* race *fumosa* Sagarra, 1926. Butll. Inst. Catal. Hist. nat. (2)6(6-7): [135](#).
TL: Queralps (Girona prov., NE Spain).
- [JS] *Strymon (Nordmannia) acaciae* race *frigidior* Verity, 1926. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 38(7/8): [125](#).
TL: Oulx (Piedmont, NW Italy).
- [JS] *Nordmannia guichardi* Higgins, 1965. The Entomologist 98: 10.
TL: Ankara (Turkey).

Satyrium abdominalis (Gerhard, [1850])

[ORIG] *Thecla abdominalis* Gerhard, [1850]. Versuch Monogr. eur. Schmett. (8): [4, pl. 4, fig. 3a-b](#).

TL: Turkey.

[JS] *Thecla acaciae* var. *gerhardi* Staudinger, 1895. Dt. Entomol. Z. 7(2): [241-242](#).

TL: Mardin, Aintab (SE Turkey).

[JS] *Nordmannia elta* Higgins, 1964. The Entomologist 97: 197.

TL: Berlin (Germany).

Satyrium ledereri Rothschild, 1913

[ORIG] *Elycaena ledereri* Boisduval, 1848. Ann. Soc. entomol. Fr. (2)6: [xxix](#).

TL: Khardar (Azerbaijan).

[JS] *Fixsenia ledereri* ssp. *nazeri* Larsen, 1974. Alexanor 8(7): 301.

TL: Jabal Kesrouan (Lebanon).

[JS] *Satyrium ledereri* ssp. *christianae* Olivier, 1989. Phegea 17(1): [8-12, fig. 7-12](#).

TL: Mt. Karvoúni (Samos Isl., Greece).

Conclusion

This synonymic list offers a foundation for the taxonomy of Western Palearctic Pieridae.

By linking each name to its original description, it enhances transparency, accessibility, and historical accuracy. However, the list is not yet complete, and gaps remain in both hyperlinks and taxonomic data. Researchers, lepidopterists and enthusiasts are warmly invited to contribute by submitting missing hyperlinks, overlooked synonyms, or other relevant information.

Author contribution

Michel Taymans: conceptualisation, analysis, visualisation, writing - original draft, writing – review and editing.

Sylvain Cuvelier: analysis, validation, visualisation, writing – review and editing.